

The usability and scalability of the Ethereum Name Service in daily transactions

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

The Ethereum Network currently requires long and tedious addresses to send Ether. An error of one character causes the entire amount sent to be lost forever, this is more common than one would think. The Ethereum Name Service was created to solve this issue.

2. Aim

To relay the promises of using the Ethereum Name Service as well as the value in Ethereum domain names. Additionally, wide scale adaptability of Ethereum in everyday businesses through the use of the Fourier Solutions platform.

3. Conclusions

The Ethereum Name Service provides a streamlining solution to processing transactions easier for many use cases such as ICOs, transfers, etc. More details on my presentation points can be found in the CryptoMudra article I published on the Ethereum Name Service: <http://www.cryptomudra.com/2017/08/etherscan-based-ethereum-name-service/>

4. Keywords

Ethereum; Blockchain; ENS; Ethereum Name Service

Author biography

Orest Byskosh Orest Byskosh, Northwestern University student studying Mathematical Methods in the Social Sciences (MMSS), Mathematics and Economics. Orest Byskosh previously served as a Research Assistant at Northwestern University's Feinberg School of Medicine where he worked with Matlab to process large data sets. He has published for CryptoMudra on the Ethereum Name Service.

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